

THE USE OF PEDAGOGICAL TECHNOLOGIES IN THE DEVELOPMENT OF STUDENTS' SKILLS OF MAKING ANALOGICAL CONCLUSIONS IN RELATION TO HISTORICAL REALITY

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Abstract: In this article, theoretical-methodological foundations of students' development of analogical conclusion skills in relation to historical reality, methodology of students' development of analogical conclusion skills in relation to historical reality are studied. Also, the use of pedagogical technologies in the development of students' skills of making analogical conclusions in relation to historical reality are analyzed.

Key words: historical reality, analogical conclusion, skill, pedagogical process, professional-pedagogical activity, integrative, corporate, national, historical, technological, competence, innovative model, technological system.

INTRODUCTION. Currently, it is desirable to use pedagogical technologies, innovations and interactive methods in the educational process, to implement newly produced technical tools, to encourage more students to work independently, and to widely use various ways of teaching lessons from best practices. Another important aspect is the teaching of special subjects in order to develop professional inclinations, abilities, knowledge and skills of students studying in higher education institutions, to acquire one or more modern professions in the fields of their choice. effective organization should be ensured.

LITERATURE ANALYSIS AND METHODS. Scientific research works on formation of knowledge and skills about historical reality, development of historical consciousness and memory, improvement of historical thinking J.Anderson, D.Blazar, S.A.Henry, K.Halbert, Helen Timperley, Aaron Wilson, Heather Barrar, L.N.Aleksashina , V.V.Barabanov, P.A.Baranov, L.S.Bakhmutova, O.Y.Strelava, M.V.Korotkova, M.T.Studenikin, N.N.Lazukova, Y.M.Persanova, E.Yusupov, J.Tulenov, A.Begmatov, N.Zhorayev, A.Choriyev, O.Gaibullayev . Nishonova, U. Mahkamov, E. Turdikulov, R. Safarova, B. Adizov, A. Choriyev, Sh. Mardonov, D. Roziyeva, N. Egamberdiyeva, Sh. Shodmonova, Sh. Sharipov, O. Jamoldinova in their scientific research found his reflection.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION. In modern conditions, it is demanded that the educational process should be directed to the development, socialization and improvement of independent critical and analytical, creative and analytical

thinking skills. For this, it is necessary to train highly qualified specialists according to the requirements of consumers, to ensure that students are trained to independently acquire knowledge and practical activities in the formation of knowledge, skills and qualifications in their chosen specialties.

The importance of developing the skills of making analogical conclusions in relation to historical reality among students is very high today, which is explained by the following aspects.

First of all, the changes taking place in the world and in our country, today's political reality and daily life needs did not reduce the public's interest in history, but on the contrary, led to a sharper perception of the past. This is a legitimate process, because the new period of change cannot be limited to a superficial study of the past. It requires a thorough understanding of all periods and processes. Because tomorrow will not be bright for people who do not remember their past. If the nation wants to see its bright future, its memory must be awake. Therefore, it is necessary for any nation and nation to draw the necessary conclusions and lessons from the past life, from the difficult and difficult days it has gone through, from the tests of history. Therefore, "creating the true scientific history of our state and nation has become an extremely important and urgent issue for our general public.

Secondly, turning points in the life of nations, wars and revolutions, transition from economic growth to depression and decline, fundamental changes in the life of society have always increased interest in history. The new stage of Uzbekistan's development has put on the agenda issues related to the choice of further development paths, that is, the methods, forms, and principles of evaluating the traveled path and developing programs for the future. The answer to such questions encourages any society to re-understand the reasons that lead to the current situation in the form of each new generation.

Thirdly, today, interest in the past, seeking to find answers for the present, and choosing a path of development in order to anticipate the future are becoming common. Because understanding the past, present and future in an integral relationship allows making the right social decisions.

Fourthly, all the changes implemented in life should take into account the mentality of the people, their historical-analytical thinking, knowledge and skills, historical and national characteristics, traditions and customs, their own tmishi comes from a deep knowledge of all the beautiful things accumulated by the talented people of Uzbekistan during the rich history of many centuries.

Fifth, being aware of the legacy of their great ancestors creates in the young generation not only a sense of pride in their history, but also a responsibility to be worthy of it and take an example from it. In Uzbekistan, young people constitute a large socio-demographic layer as the heirs of the future. The future of our country largely depends on how effectively the issues of forming the spiritual world of this young generation are solved.

There are 8 pedagogical requirements that are very effective in developing students' skills of making analogical conclusions about historical reality. To them:

1. Not as an object (vessel) that should be entered into the student's information, but as a person (subject), that is, he is formed, has his own thoughts and opinions, beliefs, views, aspirations, will, character view as a subject. This requirement requires that the teacher aligns his views with the views and teachings that are valuable to him, instead of the student's independently formed worldview, not considering it as non-existent or erasing it. requires him to act in the manner of grafting.

2. It is a requirement to try to make the best possible use of existing conditions.

3. The knowledge that the teacher wants to share with the student should be well understood and acceptable to him, in other words, it should come from him.

4. The teacher himself is not a simple automaton (radio, computer, telescreen, etc.) that transmits some foreign information to the student, but he has his own thoughts and views on the subjects of the lessons he teaches, It is a requirement to be a free and creative person who can form and express his ideas and goals independently and has strong analytical thinking.

5. It means that the knowledge and information that the pedagogue wants to give to students should be organized in a way that interests and attracts many people.

6. The teacher requires his students to create an opportunity for free exchange of ideas and communication with him during the lesson. That is, the teacher should create conditions for his students to freely ask him questions, and if necessary, express their thoughts and opinions, and encourage them to do so.

7. It is expedient for the teacher to choose and organize lesson materials taking into account the existence of relevant objective and subjective conditions for students' learning.

8. It is permissible for a teacher to be able to look at himself through the eyes of a student, not to be afraid to notice his own defects through them, and, if necessary, to change himself. For this, he needs to be able to see each student as an individual and try not to touch their pride.

Peculiar pedagogical features of developing students' skills of making analogical conclusions in relation to historical reality are as follows:- a comprehensive approach to the education of future history teachers, formation of socio-philosophical knowledge in them along with specialized subjects, questioning of the educational process organization on the basis of the latest pedagogical technologies; - to create a formative scientific environment for future history teachers as a deep and critical thinking, creative, objective person who develops the skills of drawing analogical conclusions; - in the pedagogical process of future history teachers introducing the innovative method of developing logical thinking and analytical thinking, which is very useful in their professional activities; - instilling in future history teachers the ability to work with a team, adaptability to the era, social environment, and the ability to solve problems on the spot it is necessary to give special knowledge about the formation of opportunities, to form these characteristics;

- in the training of future history teachers, it is necessary to develop historical thinking in addition to improving their knowledge of history;

- to develop a methodology for working with practical "cases" in the training of future history teachers, not limited to theoretical knowledge. Therefore, today's task of education is to teach students to be able to work independently in the conditions of an information-educational environment that is increasing day by day, to use the flow of information rationally through conscious analytical thinking.

It is known that according to the social nature of a person, he sets his own way of life and manages himself. Through the process of realizing his dreams, hopes and goals, he can turn abstract situations into real reality, materialize and use them through benefit. Good and bad, generosity and avarice, cheerfulness and unkindness, love and hatred define his whole spiritual value.

Future history teachers will experience these situations in the process of studying history and will create their own world. Also, the views that students have in order to know the human ability, intelligence, intellectual capabilities and human values in general, who are its organizer and active participant, in other words, subject, in understanding history in any conditions, and give an impartial assessment to it, are correct. they should come to the conclusion that it

can be formed only because of the foundation. Because it is only because of man that historical processes can fully demonstrate their humanitarian essence and universal values in the real sense.

CONCLUSION. The analysis of the modern approach to the quality of education shows that future history teachers should be able to independently improve their knowledge, experience, and solve everyday problems using life experience, create a database, and choose the main ones. and being able to analyze them is one of the effective factors. This situation increases the creative activity of future teachers, creates a basis for the development of informational and analytical competence, which is very important for students to choose their career path.

In conclusion, various factors influence the development of students' skills of making analogical conclusions in relation to historical reality, and it is necessary to systematize them in higher education in general, and to create an innovative pedagogical process aimed at this process.

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